

Centralizer of M-power soft computer Techniques and its Application

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Abstract: In this article we study a new type of soft ring structure known as M- power soft ring based on some ideas on M- soft sets and T_s normed operations on M-sets we also define M- power triangular normed soft ring and M-power triangular normed soft ideals and investigate some of their properties. We study some ideas in ring theory based on M -power triangular normed soft concept and its uses in ring structure. Finally, we give relationship between them.

Key words: M-sets, soft set, M-power ring, s-norm, triangular norm, M- power soft ideal, pre-image, homomorphism.

1. Introduction

The theory of soft sets, introduced by Molodtsov [1], is an extension of set theory for the study of intelligent systems characterized by insufficient and incomplete information. Maji et al. [2] defined an application of soft set theory in a decision making problem by using the rough sets and they conducted a theoretical study on soft sets in a detailed way [3]. Chen et al. [4] explained a reasonable definition of parameterizations reduction of soft collections and compared them with the concept of attributes reduction in rough set theory. The algebraic structures of set theories which deal with uncertainties have been studied by some authors. Rosenfeld [5] proposed fuzzy groups to establish results for the algebraic structures of fuzzy sets. Fuzzification of algebraic structures was studied by many authors [5–7]. Many papers on soft algebras have been published since Aktas and Cagman [8] introduced the notion of a soft group in [13]. Recently, Jun et al. [9] studied soft ideals and idealistic of BCK/BCI algebras. Acar et al.[10] introduced initial concepts of soft rings. Aygunoglu and Aygun [11] introduced the concept of fuzzy soft group and, in the meantime, they studied its properties and structural characteristics. Atagun and Sezgin [12] introduced and studied the idea of soft sub rings, soft ideal of a ring, and soft sub fields of a field. In this paper, we introduce the order of the soft structure of the group theory of power of the soft sets combined with soft group. Also characterize the m-power soft subgroups and its determination is defined.

2. Preliminaries

U , E and $P(U)$ denote the initial universal set, the set of parameters and power set of U , respectively, also $A \subseteq E$.

2.1. Definition

A pair (δ, E) is called a softset over U if δ is a mapping given by $\delta : E \rightarrow P(U)$.

2.2. Definition

For a non - empty subset B of E . The softset (δ, E) over U statistics the following condition $\delta(x) = \emptyset$ for all $x \notin B$, is called B - soft set over U and is denoted by δ_B . In other words, an B - softset δ_B over U is a function $\delta_B : E \rightarrow P(U)$ such that $\delta_B(x) = \emptyset, \forall x \notin B$. A softset over U can be represented by the set of ordered pairs $\delta_B = \{(x, \delta_B(x))/x \in E, \delta_B(x) \in P(U)\}$. It is noted that a softset is a parameterized family of subsets of U . A softset $\delta_B(x)$ may be arbitrary. Some of them may be empty and some may have non-empty intersection. We denote the set of all soft sets over U by $\tilde{\delta}(U)$. Let $\delta_B \in \tilde{\delta}(U)$ then

- (i) If $\delta_B = \emptyset$, for all $x \in E$.The δ_B is an empty soft set and denoted by δ_\emptyset .
- (ii) If $\delta_B(x) = U$ for all $x \in B$, The δ_B is an B -universal soft set and denoted by $\delta_{\bar{B}}$.
- (iii) If $\delta_B(x) = U$ and $B = E$ for all $x \in E$, it is said that $\delta_{\bar{B}}$ is a universal soft set and denoted by $\delta_{\bar{E}}$

2.3. Definition

Let $\delta_B, \delta_C \in \tilde{\delta}(U)$ be two soft sets over U .

- (i) $\delta_B(x) \subset \delta_C(x)$, for all $x \in E$, then δ_B is softsubset of δ_C and is denoted by $\delta_B(x) \subset \delta_C(x)$.
- (ii) If $\delta_B(x) \subseteq \delta_C(x)$, for all $x \in E$, then δ_B is a proper subset of δ_C and is denoted by $\delta_B \subseteq \delta_C$.
- (iii) If $\delta_B(x) \neq \delta_C(x)$, for atleast one $x \in E$, then δ_B is not soft equal δ_C , and denoted by $\delta_B \neq \delta_C$.

2.4. Definition

The intersection and union of two soft sets δ_B and δ_C are respectively, denoted by $\delta_B \tilde{\cap} \delta_C = \delta_{B \cap C}$ and $\delta_B \tilde{\cup} \delta_C = \delta_{B \cup C}$ and define by $\delta_{B \cup C}(x) = \min\{\delta_B(x), \delta_C(x)\}$ and $\delta_{B \cap C}(x) = \max\{\delta_B(x), \delta_C(x)\}$,the complement δ_B^c of δ_B is defined by $\delta_B^c(x) = 1 - \delta_B$ for all $x \in X$. Note that $(\delta_B^c)^c = \delta_B$ and $\delta_{\bar{B}}^c = \delta_B$.

2.5. Proposition

Let $\delta_B \in \tilde{\delta}(U)$ then

- (i) $\delta_B \tilde{\cup} \delta_B = \delta_B; \delta_B \tilde{\cap} \delta_B = \delta_B;$
- (ii) $\delta_B \tilde{\cup} \delta_\emptyset = \delta_B; \delta_B \tilde{\cap} \delta_\emptyset = \delta_\emptyset;$
- (iii) $\delta_B \tilde{\cup} \delta_E = \delta_E; \delta_B \tilde{\cap} \delta_E = \delta_B;$
- (iv) $\delta_B \tilde{\cup} \delta_B^c = \delta_E; \delta_B^c \tilde{\cup} \delta_B^c = \delta_\emptyset;$

2.6. Note

Algebraic structures $(\tilde{\delta}(U), \tilde{\cap})$ and $(\tilde{\delta}(U), \tilde{\cup})$ are commutative semigroup.

2.7. Note

Let δ_B, δ_C and $\delta_D \in \bar{\delta}(U)$ then

- (i) Distributive law
- (ii) Demorgon's law exists
- (iii) Associative law

2.8. Definition

Let $\delta_B, \delta_C \in \delta(U)$, the \wedge product and \vee -product of δ_B and δ_C define by $\delta_B \wedge \delta_C$ and $\delta_B \vee \delta_C$ are define by $\delta_B \wedge_C(x, y) = T\{\delta_B(x), \delta_C(y)\}$ and $\delta_B \vee_C(x, y) = S\{\delta_B(x), \delta_C(y)\} \forall x, y \in E$.

2.9. Definition

Let G be a group and $\delta \in \bar{\delta}(U)$ then δ_G is called a M -power soft T -normed groupoid (MPSTNG) over U if

$$\delta_G(x, y)^m \geq T\{\delta_G(x)^m, \delta_G(y)^m\}, \forall x, y \in G. \quad (1)$$

If δ_G is M -power soft subgroup over U , then equation is satisfies $\delta_G(x)^m = \delta_G(x)^m \forall x, y \in G$

2.10. Theorem

Let R be a ring and $\delta_G \in \bar{\delta}(U)$ then δ_G is called M -power soft T -normed ring (MPSTNR) over U if and only if

- (i) $\delta_R(x - y)^m \geq T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\}$
- (ii) $\delta_R(xy)^m \geq T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\} \forall x, y \in R$.

Proof. Assume that δ_R is an M -power soft T -normed ring over U , then

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_R(x + y)^m &\geq T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\} \\ \text{and } \delta_R(-x)^m &= \delta_R(x)^m. \end{aligned}$$

Thus obtained

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_R(x - y)^m &\geq T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(-y)^m\} \\ &= T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\}. \end{aligned}$$

Also, δ_R is an M -power soft T -normed groupoid over U , then we get

$$\delta_R(xy)^m \geq T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\} \forall x, y \in G.$$

Conversely, suppose that

$$\delta_R(x - y)^m \geq T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\} \text{ and } \delta_R(xy)^m \geq T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\} \forall x, y \in R.$$

Let us choose $x = O_R$ Which given $\delta_R(O_R \rightarrow y)^m = \delta_R(-y)^m \geq \delta_R(y)^m$ and $\delta_R(y)^m = \delta_R(-(-y)^m) \geq \delta_R(-y)^m \forall y \in R$.

$$\text{Again } \delta_R(x + y)^m = \delta_R - (-y) \geq T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(-y)^m\} = T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\}.$$

Hence δ_R is an M -power soft T -normed ring over U . □

2.11. Definition

Let R be a ring and $\delta_R \in \bar{\delta}(U)$, then M -power soft T -normed ring (MPSTNR) is called M -power soft T -normed left ideal (MPSTNLI) over U , if $\delta_R(xy)^m \geq \delta_R(y)^m$ for all $x, y \in R$ and δ_R is called M -power soft T -normed right ideal (MPSTNRI) U , If simply called both left and right ideal over U .

3. M -power soft T -normed ideal over U

In this section, we introduce a new kind of soft ring structure called M -power soft ring based on some results on M -soft sets and T_s normed operations on M -sets we also define M -power triangular normed soft ring and M -power triangular normed soft ideals and investigate some of the properties. We obtain some results in ring theory based on M -power triangular normed soft sense and its application in ring structure. We provide relationship between them. Here also M -power soft T -normed ring is written as (MPSTNR).

3.1. Definition

Let R be a ring with two binary operations “+” “.” $\delta_R \in \bar{\delta}(U)$ is called an MPSTNR over U , if

- (i) δ_R is a MPSTNR over U with respect to “+”
- (ii) δ_R is a MPSTNR groupoid over U with respect to “.”

3.2. Example

Assume that $U = Z$ (set of interests) is the universal set and $G = Z_6$ (modulo 6) is the sub set of parameters. We define the soft set δ_R over U as follows

$$\delta_R(0) = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}, \delta_R(1) = \{0, 2, 4, 6\}$$

$$\delta_R(2) = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}, \delta_R(3) = \{0, 1, 2, 5\}$$

$$\delta_R(4) = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$$

Then, we can easily check that δ_R is a MPSTNR over U .

3.3. Theorem

Let R be a ring and $\delta_R \in \bar{\delta}(U)$ then δ_R is called an M -power soft (T_s) normed ideal over U if and only if

- (i) $\delta_R(x - y)^m \geq T_s\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\}$
- (ii) $\delta_R(xy)^m \geq S\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\} \forall x, y \in G$

Proof. Suppose δ_R is an M -power soft (T, S) normed ideal over U . then

$$\delta_R(xy)^m \geq T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\}$$

also, since $\delta_R(xy)^m \geq \delta_R(y)^m$ and $\delta_R(xy)^m \geq \delta_R(x)^m$.

$$\text{We get } \delta_R(xy)^m \geq S\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\}$$

Conversely suppose that $\delta_R(x-y)^m \geq T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\}$ and $\delta_R(xy)^m \geq S\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\}$ for all $x, y \in R$. Thus

$$\delta_R(xy)^m \geq S\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\} \geq \delta_R(y)^m \text{ and}$$

$$\delta_R(xy)^m \geq S\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\} \geq \delta_R(x)^m \text{ and}$$

$$\delta_R(xy)^m \geq S\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\},$$

Therefore δ_R is an M -power soft (T, S) -normed ideal over U . □

3.4. Proposition

Let δ_R be M -power soft T -normed ring and M -power soft a T -normed ideal over U . Then $\delta_R(x)^m \geq \delta_R(x)^m$ $\forall x \in R$

Proof. Suppose that δ_R is M -power soft T -normed ring and M -power soft T -normed ideal over U . Then for all $x \in R$

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_R(x)^m &= \delta_R(x-y)^m \\ &\geq T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\} \\ &= \delta_R(x)^m. \end{aligned}$$

□

3.5. Proposition

Let R be a ring with identity and $\delta_R \in \delta(\bar{U})$. If δ_R is an M -power soft (T, S) normed ideal over U . Then $\delta(x)^m \geq \delta_R(x/R)^m \forall x \in R$.

Proof. Assume that δ_R is a M -power soft (T, S) normed ideal over U . then $\forall x \in R$

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_R(x)^m &= \delta_R(x/R)^m \\ &\geq S\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\} \\ &= \delta_{IR}(x)^m \end{aligned}$$

□

3.6. Example

Every (T, S) -normed soft ideal of a ring R over U . Then M -power soft (T, S) -normed ideal of R over U , but the converse is not true.

Solution:

Let $U = k_4 = \{l, a, b, c\}$ (kelin-4-group) be the universal collection set and $R = Z_6$ is the soft set of parameters. Now we define soft set as follows $\delta_R(0) = \{l, b\}$, $\delta_R(1) = \{b, c\}$, $\delta_R(2) = \{a, b\}$, $\delta_R(3) = \{a, b, c\}$, $\delta_R(4) = \{a, b\}$, $\delta_R(5) = \{l, a, b, c, d\}$ this proved that δ_R is an M -power that δ_R is an M -power soft (T, S) -normed ideal of R over U . But since $\delta_R(2, 3) = \{b, c\} \not\supseteq \{a, b, c\} = \delta_R(3)$, δ_R is not a (T, S) -normed soft ideal of R over U .

3.7. Note

In a division ring R , a left (right) M -power soft (T, S) -normed ideal is a M -power soft (T, S) -normed

3.8. Proposition

Let δ_R be M -power soft T -normed ring or M -power soft (T, S) -normed ideal such that image of δ_R is ordered by inclusion for $x, y \in R$. If $\delta_R(y)^m \geq \delta_R(x)^m$ for $x, y \in R$, then $\delta_R(x)^m \geq \delta_R(x - y)^m = \delta_R(y - x)^m$.

Proof. Suppose that $\delta_R(y)^m \geq \delta_R(x)^m$ for $x, y \in R$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Then } \delta_R(x - y)^m \geq T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\} &= \delta_R(x)^m \\ \delta_R(x)^m &= \delta_R(x - y + y)^m \\ &\geq T\{\delta_R(x - y)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\} \end{aligned}$$

It is given that $\delta_R(y)^m \geq \delta_R(x)^m$ and $\delta_R(x)^m \geq T\{\delta_R(x - y)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\}$ for any $x, y \in R$, then $\delta_R(x - y)^m \not\geq \delta_R(x)^m$.

Hence the theorem. □

3.9. Theorem

Let δ_R be a M -power soft (T, S) -normed ring or M -power soft (T, S) -normed ideal over U with image $\delta_R = \emptyset, \neq$ when $\emptyset \neq \neq \subset U$. If A_R and B_R are M -power soft (T, S) -normed ideals over U and $\delta_R = A_R \cup B_R$ then either $A_R(x)^m \leq B_R(x)^m$ or $B_R(x)^m \subseteq A_R(x)^m$.

Proof. Assume that $A_R(x)^m \geq B_R(x)^m$ and $B_R(y)^m \leq A_R(y)^m \forall x, y \in R$. It is given that $\delta_R = A_R \cup B_R$, thus

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_R(x)^m = A_R(x)^m &\geq B_R(x)^m \geq \phi \text{ and} \\ \delta_R(y)^m = A_R(y)^m &\geq B_R(y)^m \geq \phi. \end{aligned}$$

Since image $\delta_R = \{\phi, \psi\}$, then it follows that

$$\delta_R(x)^m = \psi = \delta_R(y)^m = A_R(x)^m = B_R(y)^m = \delta_R(x - y)^m$$

Then by Preposition (5.3.7) We get $A_R(y)^m \leq \psi = B_R(y)^m$ and $A_R(x)^m \leq \psi = B_R(x)^m$. □

3.10. Theorem

Let δ_R and δ_G be two M -power soft T -normed rings over U . Then δ_R and δ_G is M -power soft T -normed ring over U .

Proof. Let $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2) \in R \times G$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{R \wedge G}(((x_1, y_1) - (x_2, y_2))^m) &= \delta_{R \wedge G}(x_1 - x_2, y_1 - y_2)^m \\ &= T\{\delta_R(x_1 - x_2)^m, \delta_G(y_1 - y_2)^m\} \\ &\geq T\{T\{\delta_R(x_1)^m, \delta_R(x_2)^m\}, T\{\delta_G(y_1)^m, \delta_G(y_2)^m\}\} \\ &= T\{T\{\delta_R(x_1)^m, \delta_G(y_1)^m\}, T\{\delta_R(x_2)^m, \delta_G(y_2)^m\}\} \\ &= T\{\delta_{R \wedge G}(x_1, y_1)^m, \delta_{R \wedge G}(x_2, y_2)^m\} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 \delta_R \wedge_G (((x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2))^m) &= \delta_R \wedge_G (x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2)^m \\
 &= T\{\delta_R(x_1 x_2)^m, \delta_G(y_1 y_2)^m\} \\
 &\geq T\{T\{\delta_R(x_1)^m, \delta_R(x_2)^m\}, T\{\delta_G(y_1)^m, \delta_G(y_2)^m\}\} \\
 &= T\{T\{\delta_R(x_1)^m, \delta_G(y_1)^m\}, T\{\delta_R(x_2)^m, \delta_G(y_2)^m\}\} \\
 &= T\{\delta_R \wedge_G (x_1, y_1)^m, \delta_R \wedge_G (x_2, y_2)^m\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\delta_R \wedge_G$ is an M -power soft T -normed ring over U . $\delta_R \wedge_G$ is not an M -power soft T -normed soft ring. \square

4. Centralizer of M -power soft T -normed structure

4.1. Definition

Let R be a ring and $\delta_R, A_R \in \bar{\sigma}(u)$ the operations $\delta_R + A_R, \delta_R - A_R, \delta_R A_R$ defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\delta_R + A_R)(x)^m &\geq U\{T\{\delta_R(y)^m, A_R(z)^m / y, z \in R, y + z = x\}\} \\
 (\delta_R - A_R)(x)^m &\geq U\{T\{\delta_R(y)^m, A_R(z)^m / y, z \in R, y - z = x\}\} \\
 (-\delta_R)(x)^m &\geq \delta_R(x)^m \\
 (\delta_R A_R)(x)^m &\geq U\{T\{\delta_R(y)^m, A_R(z)^m / y, z \in R, yz = x\}\} \forall x \in R
 \end{aligned}$$

The operations $\delta_R + A_R, \delta_R - A_R$ and $\delta_R A_R$ are respectively M -power soft T -normed sum, difference, product of δ_R and A_R and $-\delta_R$ is called negative of δ_R .

4.2. Theorem

If R be a ring and $\delta_R, A_R, f_R \in \bar{\delta}(u)$, then $\delta_R(A_R + f_R) \leq (\delta_R A_R) + (\delta_R f_R)$

Proof. Suppose $x, y, z \in R$ such that $x = yz$. Then $\delta_R(A_R + f_R)(x)^m \geq U\{T\{\delta_R(y)^m, (A_R + f_R)(z)^m / y, z \in R, x = yz\}\}$ and

$$\begin{aligned}
 T\{\delta_R(y)^m, (A_R + f_R)(z)^m\} &= T\{\delta_R(y)^m, U\{T(A_R(w), f_R(w'))\} / w, w' \in R, w + w' = z\} \\
 &= U\{T\{\delta_R(y)^m, A_R(w)^m\}, T\{\delta_R(y)^m, f_R(w')^m\} / yw + yw' = yz\} \\
 &\leq U\{T\{\delta_R A_R(wy)^m, \delta_R f_R(w'y)^m / w, w' \in R, wy + w'y = zy\}\} \\
 &= (\delta_R A_R) + (\delta_R f_R)(x)^m
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\delta_R(A_R + f_R) \leq (\delta_R A_R) + (\delta_R f_R)$. \square

4.3. Theorem

Let δ_R be a right M -power soft T -normed ideal and A_R be a left M -power soft T -normed ideal over U . Then $\delta_R A_R \leq (\delta_R \cap A_R)$.

Proof. let $\delta_R A_R(x)^m \neq \phi$. Then $\delta_R A_R \subseteq \delta_R \cap f_R$ must hold. Assume that $\delta_R A_R(x)^m \neq \phi$ and $(\delta_R A_R)(x)^m \geq U\{T\{\delta_R(y)^m, f_R\}/y, z \in R, yz = x\}$ Since δ_R is a right M -power soft T -normed ideal and A_R is a left M -power soft T -normed ideal, then $\delta_R(x)^m = \delta_R(yz)^m \geq \delta_R(y)^m$, and

$$A_R(x)^m = A_R(yz)^m \geq A_R(z)^m$$

There fore

$$\begin{aligned} (\delta_R A_R)(x)^m &= U\{T\{\delta_R(y)^m, A_R(z)^m\}/y, z \in R, x = yz\} \\ &\leq T\{\delta_R(x)^m, A_R(x)^m\} \\ &= (\delta_R \cap A_R)(x)^m \end{aligned}$$

Thus $\delta_R A_R \leq (\delta_R \cap f_R)$. □

4.4. Definition

Let δ_R be an M -power soft T -normed ring over U . Then center of δ_R and is denote by $C\delta_R$ and is define by $C\delta_R = \{x \in R/\delta_R(x)^m = \delta_R(O_R)^m\}$.

4.5. Theorem

Let δ_R be an M -power soft T -normed ring over U . Then center of the ring $C\delta_R$ is a subring of R .

Proof. In a center of ring $O_R \in C\delta_R \subseteq R$. Let $x, y \in C\delta_R$. Then $\delta_R(x)^m = \delta_R(y)^m = \delta_R(O_R)^m$ so,

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_R(x - y)^m &\geq T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\} \\ &= T\{\delta_R(O_R)^m, \delta_R(O_R)^m\} \\ &= \delta_R(O_R)^m \end{aligned}$$

From proposition(5.3.5) , we have that $\delta_R(O_R)^m \geq \delta_R(x - y)^m$. Therefore $\delta_R(O_R)^m = \delta_R(x - y)^m$ and so $x - y \in C\delta_R$ and $xy \in C\delta_R$. Therefore $C\delta_R$ is a subring of ring R . □

4.6. Theorem

Let δ_R be an M -power soft T -normed ideal over U . Then center of the ring $C\delta_R$ is an ideal of R .

Proof. The proof of the theorem is similar as that of above theorem. □

4.7. Definition

Let δ_R be an M -power soft T -normed ring over U and α be a subset of U . Then α - inclusion of a softset δ_R , denote by δ_R^α is define as follows $\delta_R^\alpha = \{x \in R/\delta_R(x)^m \geq \alpha\}$

4.8. Theorem

Let δ_R be an M -power soft T -normed ring over U and $\alpha \subseteq \delta_R(O_R)^m$ then δ_R^α is a subring of R ,

Proof. It is easily seen that $O_R \in \delta_R^\alpha \in R$. Let $x, y \in \delta_R^\alpha$, then $\delta_R(x)^m \geq \alpha$ and $\delta_R(y)^m \geq \alpha$ then it follows that

$$\delta_R(x - y)^m \geq T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\} = \alpha$$

$$\text{and } \delta_R(xy)^m \geq T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\} = \alpha.$$

Thus $x - y, xy \in \delta_R^\alpha$, hence δ_R^α is a subring of R . □

4.9. Theorem

Let δ_R be an M -power soft T -normed ideal over U and $\alpha \subseteq \delta_R(O_R)^m$. Then, δ_R^α is an M -power soft T -normed ideal over U .

Proof. The proof of the theorem is similar as that of the above theorem, □

4.10. Theorem

Let δ_R be an M -power soft T -normed ring over U . Let f be a surjective homomorphism from R to P , the image $f(\delta_R)$ is an M -power soft T -normed ring over U .

Proof. Since f is a surjective homomorphism from R to H , there exists $x, y \in R$ such that $j = p(x)$ and $k = p(y)$ for all $l, m \in f$, then

$$\begin{aligned} (f(\delta_R))(j - k)^m &= U\{\delta_R(z)^m / Z \in R, h(z) = j - k\} \\ (f(\delta_R))(j - k)^m &= U\{\delta_R(x - y)^m, /x, y \in R, p(x) = j, p(y) = k\} \\ &\geq U\{T\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\}, x, y \in R, p(x) = j, p(y) = k\} \\ &= T\{U\{(\delta_R(x)^m), /x \in R, p(x) = j\}, U\{(\delta_R(y)^m), y \in R, /p(y) = k\}\} \\ &= T\{f(\delta_R)(x)^m, f(\delta_R)(y)^m\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } (f(\delta_R))(jk)^m &= U\{\delta_R(z)^m, z \in R, p(z) = jk\} \\ &= U\{(\delta_R(xy)^m), x, y \in R, p(x) = j, p(y) = k\} \\ &\geq U\{U\{\delta_R(x)^m, \delta_R(y)^m\}/p(x) = j, p(y) = k\} \\ &= T\{U\{(\delta_R(x)^m)/x \in R, p(x) = j\}, U\{(\delta_R(y)^m)/y \in R, p(y) = j\}\} \\ &= T\{f(\delta_R)(x)^m, f(\delta_R)(y)^m\} \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the image $f(\delta_R)$ is an M -power soft T -normed ring over U . □

4.11. Theorem

Let δ_R be M -power soft T -normed ideal over U . let f be a surjective homomorphism from R to P , then image $f(\delta_R)$ is an M -power soft T -normed ideal over U .

Proof. Since f is a surjective homomorphism from R to P , then there exists $x, y \in R$ such that $j = p(x)$ and

$k = p(y)$ for all $j, k \in f$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (f(\delta_R))(jk)^m &= U\{\delta_R(z)^m / z \in R, p(z) = jk\} \\
 &= U\{\delta_R(xy)^m / x, y \in R, p(x) = j, p(y) = k\} \\
 &\geq U\{\delta_R(x)^m / x, y \in R, p(x) = j\} \\
 &= (f(\delta_R))(x)^m \text{ and} \\
 (f(\delta_R))(jk)^m &= U\{\delta_R(z)^m / z \in R, p(z) = jk\} \\
 &= U\{\delta_R(xy)^m / x, y \in R, p(x) = j, p(y) = k\} \\
 &\geq U\{\delta_R(y)^m / x, y \in R, p(x) = k\} \\
 &= (f(\delta_R))(y)^m
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the image $f(\delta_R)$ is an M -power soft T -normed ideal over U . □

4.12. Theorem

Let δ_p an M -power soft T -normed ring over U and f be a homomorphism R to P , then inverse image $f^{-1}(\delta_p)$ is an M -power soft T -normed ring over U .

Proof. For $x, y \in R$ then

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^{-1}(\delta_p)(x - y)^m &= \delta_p((x - y)^m) \\
 &= \delta_p(f(x) - f(y))^m \\
 &\geq T\{\delta_p(f(x)^m), \delta_p(f(y)^m)\} \\
 &= T\{f^{-1}(\delta_p)(x)^m, f^{-1}(\delta_p)(y)^m\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{and } f^{-1}(\delta_p)(xy)^m &= \delta_p(f(xy)^m) \\
 &= \delta_p(f(x)f(y))^m \\
 &\geq T\{\delta_p(f(x)^m), \delta_p(f(y)^m)\} \\
 &= T\{f^{-1}(\delta_p)(x)^m, f^{-1}(\delta_p)(y)^m\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence $f^{-1}(\delta_p)$ is M -power soft T -normed ring over U . □

4.13. Theorem

Let (δ_p) be an M -power soft T -normed ring over U and f be a homomorphism R to P , then inverse image $f^{-1}(\delta_p)$ is an M -power soft T -normed ideal ring over U .

Proof. For $x, y \in R$ and (δ_p) is an M -power soft T -normed ring over U (shown in the above theorem)

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^{-1}(\delta_p)(xy)^m &= \delta_p((xy)^m) \\
 &= \delta_p(f(x)f(y))^m \\
 &\geq \delta_p(f(x)^m) \\
 &= f^{-1}(\delta_p(x)^m) \\
 \text{and } f^{-1}(\delta_p)(xy)^m &= \delta_p(f(xy)^m) \\
 &= \delta_p(f(x)f(y))^m \\
 &\geq \delta_p(f(y)^m) \\
 &= f^{-1}(\delta_p(y)^m)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $f^{-1}(\delta_p)$ is an M -power soft T -normed ring over U . □

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